

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Paci****FIRST NAME: Roberta****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: World, OS Big Sur

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. The body of an essay, is the part of your research in which you:**
 - Introduce the topic with broad sentences and provide a thesis statement.
 - Restate your answer to the research questions.
 - Include a final broad statement.
 - Answer the research question by developing a discussion and offering evidences in support to your argument.¹**

- 2. With reference to paraphrasing, which statement below is incorrect :**
 - You must use your own words.
 - You should keep the same style used by the author.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-410/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 2nd ed.*(Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

² Ibid., 8.

- Information provided should represent what the author has wrote.
- You should still have to cite the source.

3. **When an online source can be considered reliable?**

- The source appear in the web site of an international organization.
- The source has been published on the web site since long time.
- The site is sponsored by a reputable organization and indicate when was last updated.³**
- The source present a good use of vocabulary.

4. **When should you use direct quotations?**

- It would be complicated to paraphrase the source.
- They are strikingly original.⁴**
- You agree with the view of the author you wish to cite.
- You are not sure about the idea expressed by the author.

5. **In revising your thesis, make sure that you:**

- Use passive form of verbs.
- Write long introductory phrases.
- Make sure that new information are at the beginning of a paragraph to catch reader attention.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago:University of Chicago Press, 2013), 29.

⁴ Ibid., 32.

Make subject short and concrete and use verbs for key actions instead of nouns.⁵

6. **Which is the order and format used by WHO style for dates:**

- Day, month and year.
- Month (pell out in full), day and year with.
- Month, day and year (all in numbers).
- Day, month (spell out in full) and year.**⁶

7. **In WHO style, when is possible to abbreviate the word figure in Fig?**

- Never.
- When referring to a generic figure.
- When referring to specific figure either in text or figure title.**⁷
- Only in figure title.

8. **Which set of methods below is used only in qualitative researches?**

- Surveys, data reviews, observations.
- Interviews, surveys and data reviews.
- Interviews, focus groups, surveys.

⁵ Ibid., 75-76.

⁶ World Health Organization, 7.

⁷ Ibid., 9.

Interviews, focus groups and observations⁸.

9. **What are the criteria to evaluate qualitative researches?**

Validity and reliability.

Realibility and transferability.

Credibility reability and validity.

Credibility, dependability and transferability.⁹

10. **How an interview should be transcribed?**

As a summary of what interviewee has said.

As a summary of what interviewee has said but adding your own observation of non-verbal elements.

Considering only words but transcribing word by word what intrviewee has said.

Verbatim, exact word by word along with eventual interruption, pauses and all non-verbal elements.¹⁰

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 73.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 77-78.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 97.

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